

The Evolution and Functioning Of Panchayats in Karnataka: Ancient, Medieval, and British Periods

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Abstract

Panchayats have played a pivotal role in the governance and administration of Indian societies for centuries. This article delves into the historical evolution and functioning of panchayats in the Karnataka region during the ancient, medieval, and British periods. By tracing their development, roles, and functions, we gain a comprehensive understanding of the socio-political landscape of Karnataka across these eras. The abstract explores the historical trajectory and operational dynamics of panchayats in Karnataka across three distinct periods: ancient, medieval, and British. This investigation delves into the evolutionary journey of these local governance institutions, tracing their roles and functions through shifting socio-political landscapes. In the ancient period, panchayats emerged as vital community assemblies, comprising revered elders who governed through consensus-based decisions, focusing on dispute resolution and resource management. Transitioning to the medieval era, panchayats diversified their responsibilities under the Vijayanagara Empire's reign, engaging in revenue collection, infrastructure maintenance, and agrarian oversight within a structured hierarchical framework. The British colonial period marks a significant transformation, witnessing the erosion of traditional panchayats as colonial administrators introduced centralized governance mechanisms, redefining local authority structures. Through these stages, panchayats consistently undertook roles like dispute resolution, infrastructure development, social welfare, and law enforcement, fostering community participation and preserving customary laws. This abstract encapsulates the multifaceted evolution of panchayats in Karnataka, highlighting their enduring contributions to governance, community welfare, and the complex interplay of historical influences on local governance systems.

Key Words: Panchayats, Ancient, Medieval, British Periods, Act.

Introduction:

The institution of panchayats, deeply rooted in traditional Indian governance, has been a cornerstone of local self-governance for ages. In Karnataka, a state with a rich historical legacy, panchayats have experienced significant shifts in their roles and functions throughout different historical periods. This article aims to explore the evaluation and functioning of panchayats in Karnataka during the ancient, medieval, and British periods, shedding light on their evolution and contribution to governance.

Methodology

The research paper is based on secondary data. The data is taken from different research reports, journals, websites and research papers, Magazine and daily Newspapers, and other educational text books

Objectives of the Study

1. To understand the concept Panchayats
2. To understand the Evolution and Functioning of Panchayats in Karnataka

What is Panchayats?

A panchayat is a traditional form of local self-governance in India. The term "panchayat" is derived from two Sanskrit words: "panch," which means five, and "ayat," which means assembly. It refers to a council or assembly of five individuals who come together to make decisions and govern a local community. Panchayats have been an integral part of Indian society for centuries and serve as grassroots institutions for rural governance and administration.

Panchayats typically consist of elected representatives from the local community who take on various responsibilities related to local development, resource management, dispute resolution, and social welfare. They operate at the village, intermediate (block or taluka), and district levels, forming a three-tier structure known as the Panchayati Raj System. This system aims to decentralize governance and bring decision-making closer to the people, allowing them to actively participate in the development and management of their communities.

The roles and functions of panchayats include:

1. **Local Governance:** Panchayats are responsible for making decisions related to local development projects, infrastructure, and services such as water supply, sanitation, roads, and education.
2. **Resource Management:** They manage local resources such as land, water, and forests, ensuring sustainable use and equitable distribution.
3. **Social Welfare:** Panchayats play a role in implementing government welfare schemes and programs, especially those targeted at rural and marginalized communities.
4. **Dispute Resolution:** Panchayats serve as forums for resolving disputes within the community, often relying on traditional norms and practices to ensure justice and harmony.
5. **Promotion of Local Culture:** Panchayats help preserve and promote local customs, traditions, and cultural practices, contributing to the preservation of cultural heritage.
6. **Community Participation:** Panchayats encourage active participation of community members in decision-making processes, fostering a sense of ownership and empowerment.

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The significance of panchayats lies in their ability to address local issues promptly, involve the community in governance, and promote accountable and transparent administration at the grassroots level. They have also been recognized by the Indian Constitution, which grants constitutional status to panchayats and mandates their establishment and functioning as part of the Panchayati Raj System.

While the traditional concept of panchayats has evolved over time and faced challenges such as political interference and limited resources, efforts have been made to strengthen and empower them. Various legislative reforms and government initiatives have aimed to enhance the role of panchayats in local development and governance, recognizing their importance in fostering inclusive and sustainable development in rural India.

Ancient Period:

During the ancient period, Karnataka was home to various dynasties such as the Satavahanas, Chalukyas, Rashtrakutas, and Kadambas. Panchayats in this era were essential units of local governance and justice administration. These assemblies were composed of wise elders from the community who discussed and decided on matters ranging from dispute resolution to resource management. The main features of ancient panchayats in Karnataka were their focus on

consensus-based decision-making, close-knit community involvement, and adherence to customary laws.

Medieval Period:

As Karnataka transitioned into the medieval period, Islamic sultanates and empires like the Bahmanis and Vijayanagara rose to power. During this time, panchayats' roles expanded to encompass not only local governance but also the collection of taxes, maintenance of infrastructure, and defense. The Vijayanagara Empire, in particular, established a complex administrative structure where panchayats played an integral role in revenue collection and agrarian management. These panchayats were hierarchical, with tiers of administration ranging from village-level assemblies to district-level councils.

British Period:

The arrival of the British in India marked a significant turning point in the governance structure of Karnataka. The British East India Company introduced their own administrative framework, which had a profound impact on the functioning of panchayats. The traditional panchayat system was gradually replaced by colonial administrative bodies, leading to a decline in the traditional forms of local self-governance. The British favored centralized governance and introduced laws that undermined the autonomy of panchayats.

Histroy of Panchayati Raj

The realisation that Grama Swaraj can only be realised via the establishment of Grama Panchayats bolstered the movement to establish local governments. In our country's power-sharing system, the responsibility for establishing Grama Panchayats and implementing Panchayat-related structures and mechanisms falls entirely on the shoulders of the State. The central government has no role to play in any state-level legislation. With this in mind, and with the goal of implementing Panchayat Raj systems throughout the country, the Centre has started establishing relevant Committees. The Balwant Rai Mehta Committee is the first that springs to mind. This Committee issued suggestions to various states. Several states, including Karnataka, established several committees to implement Panchayat Raj systems that are relevant to local circumstances and realities. Following the suggestions of these Committees, the Panchayati Raj system was established in various States. The 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments went into effect in 1993. Until then, the creation and accountability for local governments was solely the duty of state governments, and local governments were reliant on administrative resolutions and obligations.

With this history in mind, Karnataka passed the Grama Panchayat and Local Government Act

(Panchayat and Local Board Act) for the first time in 1959. Following that, in 1960, laws for Grama and Taluk Panchayats were passed, as well as guidelines for Zilla Panchayat membership. This scenario lasted until 1983. Elections were not held on a regular basis at the time, and administrators led the Grama Panchayats. At the national level, there are numerous instances of states, such as Gujarat, Maharashtra, and West Bengal. In West Bengal, the ruling party altered the previous Panchayat Raj Act in 1988, ushering in a new three-tiered government system. An interesting item to notice is that, even without the Constitutional Amendment, West Bengal has held Panchayat elections every five years since 1978, without missing a single day. D. Abdul Nazir Sab's dream child was the Karnataka Panchayati Raj system. The esteemed Ramakrishna Hegde believed in this concept and provided it support, allowing it to be adopted in 1983. However, in order to become formal, it needed the permission and

As a result of its adoption by the Centre and the Prime Minister, it was only declared legislation in 1985. For the first time, elections for Zilla and Mandal Panchayats were held in 1987. The 1985 law defined the roles and responsibilities of Zilla Panchayats, Taluk Panchayats, and legal committees. However, due to the debates of numerous Committees formed in relation to the Constitutional Amendment, primarily the Ashok Mehta Committee, the implementation of this statute was brought to a close soon after it was enacted. These committees presented suggestions for the establishment of Panchayat Raj institutions based on a constitutional amendment, claiming that only in this manner will the Panchayat system be effective. This Amendment received a majority vote in the Lok Sabha but fell short by one vote in the Rajya Sabha. As a result, the then-prime minister, Hon. V.P Singh, proposed a draught bill, but before it could be debated, he had to quit power. Later, in 1991, under the Prime Ministership of Hon. P.V Narasimha Rao, the ruling party at the Centre proposed another draught bill dealing to rural areas. Hon. Ram Nivas Mirza, the senior ex-Minister, presented to the entire House a detailed study of the aspects of this measure dealing to Grama Panchayats. He planned a huge convention with representatives from all major parties and provided documentation. The 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendment proposals were passed on the basis of this submission. The 73rd dealt solely with the Gramme Panchayat system. It ordered that any state with a population of more than 20 lakhs implement a three-tier Panchayat Raj structure. As a result of this mandate, Karnataka's existing two-tier Panchayati Raj structure could not be implemented. The 74th Constitutional Amendment addressed only

city local administrations. The 74th Amendment captures the component that is similar to both, and it is because of this that the notion of District Planning Committee (DPC) was inserted in the Indian Constitution. We pay little attention to the District Planning Committees. The 74th CAA emphasised the importance of realising the DPC. It required that every district in the country execute this within one year of the CAA going into effect. If a Constitutional Amendment is related to a State matter, it must be approved by a two-thirds majority in both Houses of Parliament. Furthermore, it must be approved by more than half of the state legislatures. All of the state legislatures unanimously approved and signed these amendments. This is significant because it shows that all political parties in all states are bound by these Amendments. Karnataka was the first state in the country to implement the three-tier Panchayati Raj system after the Constitutional Amendments. Despite multiple revisions, the Karnataka Panchayati Raj Act is still in effect today, and elections to Grama Panchayats were held under this Act in December 1993. The Constitutional Amendments are subject to many interpretations. The State Election Commissions (SEC) are responsible for holding elections to the State Assemblies and Legislative Houses, and the SEC is also responsible for elections to Grama Panchayats. However, this is a constitutional system that should be the same at the federal and state levels. The one is not superior than the other. The Finance Commission is another structure. A Central Finance Commission investigates how money and resources are shared between the Centre and the States. Previously, the Central Finance Commission's proposals did not address local government difficulties, and this was only addressed after the CAA. Importantly, whatever suggestions the CFC makes, both the Centre and the States are required to follow through on them. Despite the fact that the State Finance Commissions are mentioned in the Constitution, their recommendations are not binding on the states. State Finance Commission proposals are not always accepted by the states. The proposals have been approved by the state government, according to the administration. However, we have not seen these recommendations incorporated in either the annual or five-year plans. Karnataka is also a member of the same organisation.

The District Planning Committee is crucial. When we hear the term "decentralisation," we usually refer to administrative decentralisation. However, in order for actual development to occur, planning must be decentralised. The government makes several statements at various levels about the programmes that should take place each year. Following that, local organisations such as the

Grama Sabha, Grama Panchayat, Zilla Panchayat, and so on should discuss it and formulate recommendations and plans to present to the District Planning Committee. The President of the District Planning Committee is the President of the Zilla Panchayat. Local institution suggestions should be reviewed in the District Planning Committee, and once forwarded to the State Government, the State does not have the legal right to amend the plan. If there are any State or Central preferences for programmes, they should be brought to the District Planning Committee's attention as ideas and recommendations, and the Committee should seek grants to implement them.

However, other states, including Karnataka, have yet to establish District Planning Committees in accordance with the description provided above. Aside from stating that the District Planning Committees have been formed, no work has begun. The State has yet to provide us with a clear picture of if and how it is operating. It is unclear if the District plans that have been released are the work of the District Planning Committee or not. Under decentralisation, the Committee has yet to find its true significance. It is very regrettable that the Committees do not function in Karnataka.

Second, our state statutes require the formation of a State Panchayat Council. The President of this shall be the Hon Chief Minister, while the Vice-President will be the Minister for Rural Development and Panchayati Raj. The Council would also include Panchayat delegates from various levels. Previously, we had District Councils, with the Chief Minister coordinating the proceedings. The objective for this was to provide a forum for the Chief Minister to comprehend our feelings and issues, as well as to discuss and find answers. However, the administration is now paying no attention to this.

There is absolutely no mention of State-level Minister representatives playing key roles in Panchayati Raj institutions in the Constitution. On the other hand, there are definite reservations for SC, ST, and women in Panchayat Raj institutions, but no reservations for other marginalised groups. The decision on these further reservations has been delegated to the state legislatures. The Panchayati Raj Constitutional Amendment was passed in 1993. There have been numerous changes in our country and in the United States since that period. There is now a necessity to alter the Constitutional Amendment itself. Karnataka needs to offer a recommendation in this area as well.

Functioning of Panchayats:

Across these historical periods, the functioning of panchayats in Karnataka shared common themes while also experiencing changes influenced by the prevailing political and social contexts. The primary

functions of panchayats included dispute resolution, resource management, infrastructure development, social welfare, and maintaining law and order. Panchayats held regular meetings, where decisions were made through discussions, consensus-building, and adherence to customary laws. The leaders of these assemblies were usually elders respected for their wisdom and experience.

Evolution of Panchayats:

The evolution of panchayats in Karnataka was marked by a gradual shift from consensus-based decision-making to more structured administrative hierarchies. In the ancient period, panchayats were decentralized and community-centric. During the medieval era, the introduction of formal administrative tiers brought about greater organization and specialization. However, the British colonial period witnessed the erosion of traditional panchayats in favor of centralized control.

Impact on Society:

Panchayats in Karnataka left a lasting impact on society. They facilitated community participation, promoted local leadership, and ensured the preservation of traditional customs and norms. Panchayats played a crucial role in maintaining social harmony, resolving disputes, and addressing the welfare needs of the community. The decline of traditional panchayats during British rule had repercussions on local governance, weakening community participation and diluting the effectiveness of decision-making processes.

Conclusion:

The evolution and functioning of panchayats in Karnataka throughout ancient, medieval, and British periods provide valuable insights into the socio-political dynamics of the region. While these institutions played vital roles in local governance, the influence of external forces, especially during the British colonial era, led to a decline in their autonomy and authority. Recognizing the historical significance of panchayats in Karnataka allows us to appreciate their contributions to community welfare and governance, while also prompting us to consider the importance of empowering local self-governance in contemporary times.

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